

A new strategy to design and implement the optimal Multi-Antenna Broadcast Channel precoder

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Abstract—Even though the sum capacity of decentralized schemes, either at transmission or reception, has already been computed, in the literature, there is a lack of practical implementation schemes that achieve this sum capacity. This paper presents a novel precoder design for the multi-antenna Broadcast Channel (BC) in order to attain the BC sum capacity. It is a non-iterative BC architecture, which first implements the so-called embedded power loading. This consists in including the equivalent point-to-point (PtP) multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) optimal power waterfilling and eigenbeamforming. As the resulting equivalent channel is not diagonal and the decentralized receivers cannot cooperate to cancel the interference, as in the PtP MIMO case, the rest of the precoder is devoted to reproduce residual interference of the optimal dual MAC, which has been previously computed. In order not to introduce additional power, only orthogonal transformations together with a THP are used for that. A numerical example illustrates the proposed new strategy and implementation.

Index Terms—Sum capacity, Broadcast channel, MIMO, Tomlinson-Harashima, precoding

I. INTRODUCTION

In broadcast multiple input multiple output (MIMO) wireless cellular systems, where quality of service (QoS) is interference limited, a variety of power control, scheduling, precoding and decoding (linear and non-linear) problems can be formulated. Even though the sum capacity of the broadcast channel (BC) has already been computed, there is a lack of efficient practical schemes that can achieve it. In [1] the authors showed through direct calculation that dirty paper coding (DPC) together with linear beamforming achieves the sum capacity. Following this seminal work, new results appeared in [2], [3] and [4], which studied the case of any number of users and antennas at each reception. In [2] and [3] the concept of MAC (multiple access channel) and BC duality is used to transform the computationally complex non-convex problem in the BC into a well-studied convex problem in the MAC. In [4], the authors rely on the ideas of decision feedback equalization and its dual at transmission. Finally, deriving the results on first principles, not applying any of the above existing results, [6] provides a more complete and

self-contained view in order to prove that DPC rate region coincide with the BC capacity region. The above-mentioned works motivated iterative algorithms; such as those in [5] and [11], where the authors use the previous results and introduce convex duality to derive iterative algorithms that provide the optimum transmission policies for the MAC, which are then mapped into the optimal BC policies.

Since then, alternative strategies have been devised both in terms of linear (i.e. beamforming) and non-linear types of precoding, see [7], [8], [9] and many references therein and [10] as a recent and interesting approach to the optimum solution in a MIMO OFDM context. The literature on spatial precoding techniques is very rich, indeed. The main strategies to derive low-complex alternatives are those based on: uplink-downlink signal to noise and interference ratio (SNIR) duality, sum-rate maximization by iterative adaptation of the BC transmit matrix (either directly or by geometric programming), LR decomposition, zero-forcing and regularized pseudoinverse, modified Tomlinson-Harashima precoding or lattice reduction and, finally, opportunistic beamforming. Clearly, it is an important problem with obvious practical implications. However, it is still desirable to obtain both optimal and practical strategies, with reduce the complexity, that attain the BC sum-capacity. This is the purpose of this paper.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the signal model. Section III revisits the design for the optimal multi-antenna MAC. Section IV introduces the novel part of this work that designs the multi-antenna BC from the MAC. Finally, Section V shows simulations that support the proposed technique.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a memoryless BC with N antennas at the base station and K users with one receive antenna each. Focusing on one particular symbol time instant, the base band signal at receiver i is denoted by y_i . The stack of all K received signals is modeled as

$$\mathbf{y} = \begin{pmatrix} y_1 \\ \dots \\ y_K \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{h}_1^H \\ \dots \\ \mathbf{h}_K^H \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{x}_{BC} + \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{H}^H \mathbf{x}_{BC} + \mathbf{w}, \quad (1)$$

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where \mathbf{H} is the $K \times N$ complex channel matrix, whose columns contain each of the user channel vectors, \mathbf{h}_i $i = 1 \dots K$. The vector \mathbf{x}_{BC} contains the precoded symbols that are sent by each of the N transmit antenna. Specifically, $\mathbf{x}_{BC} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{i}$. \mathbf{B} is the $N \times K$ precoding matrix to be designed and \mathbf{i} stacks the K symbols to be transmitted to each of the K users at each symbol time. Each symbol energy is considered that is normalized to one (i.e., $E(\mathbf{i}\mathbf{i}^H) = \mathbf{I}$). Finally \mathbf{w} is a complex Gaussian vector of zero mean and \mathbf{R}_o correlation matrix, which models the thermal noise. Still, in the next sections, the system model in (1) is used to develop the baseline designs in terms of the point-to-point and the MAC transmission.

III. POINT-TO-POINT MIMO SUM CAPACITY

Before tackling the actual problem of the paper, i.e. the multi-antenna BC, this section is devoted to the PtP MIMO transmission. In other words, this section considers (1) as a PtP signal model, in which the unique receiver has access to the entire received vector \mathbf{y} . The reason for considering here the PtP MIMO transmission is that not only it is a baseline design, whose performance upper bounds that of the BC, but also its strategy will be used in the BC.

The sum capacity of the PtP is the maximization of the mutual information in (2) with respect to $\mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}^H$ when $\text{Trace}(\mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}^H) \leq E_T$

$$\begin{aligned} MI_{PtP} &= \log \det (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{H}\mathbf{R}_o^{-1}\mathbf{H}^H\mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}^H) \\ &= \log \det (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{R}_H\mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}^H). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Since for definite positive matrices, its determinant is upper bounded by the product of its diagonal elements, the optimal solution for \mathbf{B} is the one that diagonalizes the normalized channel correlation, \mathbf{R}_H , and allocates the optimal power waterfilling to each channel mode. Therefore, if the singular value decomposition (SVD) of the normalized channel is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R}_o^{-1/2}\mathbf{H}^H &= \mathbf{V}\mathbf{D}_H^{1/2}\mathbf{U}^H \\ \mathbf{R}_H &= \mathbf{U}\mathbf{D}_H\mathbf{U}^H, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

the optimal PtP precoding matrix is

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{D}_{WF}^{1/2}\mathbf{M}, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{D}_{WF} is a $K \times K$ diagonal matrix that contains the optimal waterfilling powers, \mathbf{M} is any orthonormal matrix, i.e., $\mathbf{M}\mathbf{M}^H = \mathbf{I}$, and does not modify the capacity. That is, \mathbf{M} introduces additional degrees of freedom that can be useful as we will see later.

With that the equivalent MIMO channel is

$$\mathbf{H}_e = \mathbf{R}_o^{-1/2}\mathbf{H}^H\mathbf{U}\mathbf{D}_{WF}^{1/2} = \mathbf{V}(\mathbf{D}_H\mathbf{D}_{WF})^{1/2}, \quad (5)$$

and the receiver must multiply by \mathbf{V}^H the received signal vector \mathbf{y} in order to eliminate the multiuser interference.

However, in the multi-antenna BC the receivers cannot cooperate to eliminate the interference. Therefore, the question that this paper addresses is if we can design a transmitter

matrix \mathbf{M} able to precancel as much as possible this interference and attain the BC sum-capacity. Note that due to the receiver coordination in the PtP, the sum-capacity of the PtP MIMO is an upper bound of the sum-capacity of the BC. In other words, since the capacity region of a general BC depends only on the marginal transition probabilities of the channel (i.e., $p(y_i/\mathbf{x})$ and not on the joint distribution $p(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_K/\mathbf{x})$), correlation between the noise samples at different receivers of the BC does not affect the BC capacity region. It does, however, affect the capacity of the cooperative system, which is still an upper bound on the sum-capacity of the BC. In [11], the authors prove that the sum-capacity of the PtP scenario for the worst-case noise correlation (i.e., so-called Sato upper bound) equals the sum-capacity of the BC. Interestingly, by using Lagrangian duality, the Sato upper bound can also be formulated as the sum-capacity of the MAC when there is a constraint on the total transmission power (see [11]). This is a key result because, in contrast to the non-convex BC sum-capacity problem, the sum-capacity of the MAC is a convex problem that can be solved with various low-complexity iterative algorithms. This rationale supports the existing implementations in the literature for the optimal BC precoding, based on the so-called MAC-BC duality or downlink-uplink duality (e.g., [4], [5]). Namely, once the optimal power allocation of the MAC is obtained then some MAC-to-BC transformation formulas are applied to obtain the optimal BC design. The present work proposes an alternative implementation of this duality.

IV. MULTI-ANTENNA MAC SUM CAPACITY

If we depart from (1), in the MAC, the transmitters do not cooperate, but the receiver. That is, there is only one receiver with N multiple antennas and K transmitters or users with one antenna each; thus the channel is \mathbf{H} instead of \mathbf{H}^H . We say that the model of the N received signals, stack in the vector \mathbf{y}_{MAC} is the dual of that in (1)

$$\mathbf{y}_{MAC} = (\mathbf{h}_1 \dots \mathbf{h}_K) \mathbf{x}_{MAC} + \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}_{MAC} + \mathbf{w}. \quad (6)$$

Note that, due to the properties of the determinant, the mutual information of the dual channel \mathbf{H} is the same as that of \mathbf{H}^H in (2), but constrained by the fact that the transmitters do not cooperate and, therefore, the precoder must be diagonal, i.e., $\mathbf{B}^H\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{D}_{MAC}$, where \mathbf{D}_{MAC} is a diagonal matrix. Each element of the diagonal is the maximum transmit power for each user.

Due to the non-cooperation at transmission, in the MAC, the transmitters cannot diagonalize the channel and the sum-capacity of the MAC is clearly upper bounded by that of the MIMO PtP transmission. However, by convex Lagrangian duality it can be proved that it coincides with the Sato upper bound if the transmitters are allowed to exchange transmitting power with a total power constraint. That is

$$\max_{\mathbf{B}^H\mathbf{B}=\mathbf{D}_{MAC}, \text{Trace}\mathbf{D}_{MAC} \leq E_T} \log \det (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{R}_H^H\mathbf{B}^H\mathbf{B}). \quad (7)$$

Note that this optimization problem is convex and there are various iterative algorithms in the literature to obtain the

optimal $\mathbf{D}_{MAC}^{opt} = \text{diag}(E_1^{opt}, \dots, E_K^{opt})$. As commented before, it can be proved that the capacity of the multi-antenna BC coincides with the Sato upperbound (e.g., [11]); therefore, we can apply the MAC-BC channel duality to design the BC precoder from the MAC. In this way, the K user rates that are attained in the MAC when \mathbf{D}_{MAC}^{opt} and the optimal MAC receiver are implemented, can also be achieved in the BC, after a proper user reordering. Next section, proposes a novel BC precoder design based on this principle. First, the optimal MAC receiver, which allows the sum-rate to attain the sum-capacity, is presented. It is the so-called Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) sequential interference canceller (SIC). Although it is well-known in the literature (e.g., [3], [4], [9]), we recapitulate it in the next subsection for the sake of clarity of the present work, because in this work the residual multiuser interference in the MAC is used to develop the baseline design of the BC.

A. Design of the multi-antenna MAC receiver that attains the sum-capacity

The sum-capacity depends on the transmitter design and the channel and it indicates the maximum sum-rate that can be reached with a probability of error tending to zero. In that sense, the design of the receiver must be such that it guarantees that this maximum sum-rate can be attained. For that purpose, first we order the columns in \mathbf{H} . We denote by \mathbf{H}_{or} the resulting matrix. Next, we introduce a receive beamforming matrix \mathbf{A} , whose columns are each of the beamformers, \mathbf{a}_i , that are dedicated to the proper reception of each user i . The formulation of how this matrix applies to the base band received signal \mathbf{y}_{MAC} is as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{r} &= \begin{pmatrix} r_1 \\ \dots \\ r_K \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{y}_{MAC} = \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{H}_{or} \mathbf{x}_{MAC} + \mathbf{w} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{a}_1^H \mathbf{h}_1 & \dots & \mathbf{a}_1^H \mathbf{h}_K \\ \dots \\ \mathbf{a}_K^H \mathbf{h}_1 & \dots & \mathbf{a}_K^H \mathbf{h}_K \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{x}_{MAC} + \mathbf{w}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Note that the elements outside the main diagonal of $\mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{H}$ in each row i indicate the interference that affects the desired signals of user i after beamforming. In order to cancel part of this interference a SIC is implemented, which first detects user K , subtracts it from the signal at the output of beamforming $k-1$, these two signals are subsequently subtracted from the output of beamformer $k-2$, and this is repeated till the detection of user 1. This sequential interference canceller works with negligible error propagation from the detection of one user to the next one, if user K is the one with the strongest equivalent channel and very low interference from the other users (i.e., zero or almost zero elements in row K except element K, K), and user 1 is the one with the weakest channel. In fact, the ordering of the columns in \mathbf{H}_{or} should be done so that this is achieved after applying the beamformers in \mathbf{A} . However, the beamforming matrix depends on the ordering, itself. For this reason, we propose two

suboptimal alternatives to arrange the column vectors in \mathbf{H} : i) so that \mathbf{D}_{MAC}^{opt} presents $E_1^{opt} < E_2^{opt} \dots < E_K^{opt}$ or, ii) such that $|\mathbf{h}_{1,or}| < |\mathbf{h}_{2,or}| < \dots < |\mathbf{h}_{K,or}|$ in \mathbf{H}_{or} . Next, we formulate $\mathbf{R}_{MAC} = \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{H}_{or}$ indicating two kinds of interference

$$\mathbf{R}_{MAC} = \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{H}_{or} = \begin{pmatrix} r_{11} & r_{12} & r_{13} & \dots & r_{1K} \\ \epsilon_{21} & r_{22} & r_{23} & \dots & r_{2K} \\ \epsilon_{31} & \epsilon_{32} & r_{33} & \dots & r_{3K} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \epsilon_{K1} & \epsilon_{K2} & \dots & \epsilon_{K(K-1)} & r_{KK} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

Those that are denoted by $r_{ij}, i=1 \dots K, i \leq j$ are cancelled by the SIC, as commented before, while those denoted by $\epsilon_{ij}, j=1 \dots K, j \leq i$ are the residual interference at the output of the beamformer that cannot be cancelled. Although ideally, one could think that the best option is that they were zero thanks to a suitable beamforming design, next we show that the solution that allows to reach the MAC sum-capacity is when the beamformer allows a certain level of interference different from zero. It is precisely the residual interference from the MMSE beamforming. Next, we prove that for $K=2$ users, the MMSE beamformer and a subsequent SIC allow the sum-rate to reach the sum-capacity.

Let us consider that there are $K=2$ users in the MAC scenario with N antennas at the receiver. The received signal \mathbf{y} is filtered by a spatial 2×2 beamforming matrix $\mathbf{A} = (\mathbf{a}_1 \mathbf{a}_2)$. Next a SIC detects the signal from user 2, subtracts it from the output of beamforming for user 1 and detects user 1 free from interference. We formulate the corresponding rates for user 1, r_1 , and 2, $r_{2,MMSE}$, as follows

$$\begin{aligned} r_1 &= \log_2 (1 + |h_1|^2 E_1^{opt}) \\ r_{2,MMSE} &= \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{|\mathbf{a}_2^H \mathbf{h}_2|^2 E_2^{opt}}{\mathbf{a}_2^H (\mathbf{I} + E_1^{opt} \mathbf{h}_1 \mathbf{h}_1^H) \mathbf{a}_2} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where we assume that $|\mathbf{a}_i|^2 = 1, i=1,2$, and that $\mathbf{a}_1 = \frac{\mathbf{h}_1}{|\mathbf{h}_1|}$. If the beamformer for user 2 is the MMSE one

$$\mathbf{a}_2 = \frac{(\mathbf{I} + E_1^{opt} \mathbf{h}_1 \mathbf{h}_1^H)^{-1} \mathbf{h}_2}{\left(\mathbf{h}_2^H (\mathbf{I} + E_1^{opt} \mathbf{h}_1 \mathbf{h}_1^H)^{-2} \mathbf{h}_2 \right)^{1/2}}, \quad (11)$$

and then

$$\begin{aligned} r_{2,MMSE} &= \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\left(\mathbf{h}_2^H (\mathbf{I} + E_1^{opt} \mathbf{h}_1 \mathbf{h}_1^H)^{-1} \mathbf{h}_2 \right)^2 E_2^{opt}}{\left(\mathbf{h}_2^H (\mathbf{I} + E_1^{opt} \mathbf{h}_1 \mathbf{h}_1^H)^{-1} \mathbf{h}_2 \right)} \right) \\ &= \log_2 \left(1 + \left(\mathbf{h}_2^H (\mathbf{I} + E_1^{opt} \mathbf{h}_1 \mathbf{h}_1^H)^{-1} \mathbf{h}_2 \right) E_2^{opt} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

By applying the matrix inversion lemma

$$\mathbf{I} + E_1^{opt} \mathbf{h}_1 \mathbf{h}_1^H = \mathbf{I} - \frac{E_1^{opt} \mathbf{h}_1 \mathbf{h}_1^H}{1 + E_1^{opt} \mathbf{h}_1^H \mathbf{h}_1} \quad (13)$$

we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h}_2^H (\mathbf{I} + E_1^{opt} \mathbf{h}_1 \mathbf{h}_1^H)^{-1} \mathbf{h}_2 &= |\mathbf{h}_2|^2 - \frac{|\mathbf{h}_1^H \mathbf{h}_2|^2 E_1^{opt}}{1 + E_1^{opt} |\mathbf{h}_1|^2} \\ &= \frac{|\mathbf{h}_2|^2 + \delta E_1^{opt}}{1 + |\mathbf{h}_1|^2 E_1^{opt}}, \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where δ is the determinant of $\mathbf{H}_{or}^H \mathbf{H}_{or}$.

With that

$$r_{2,MMSE} = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{|\mathbf{h}_2|^2 + \delta E_1^{opt}}{1 + |\mathbf{h}_1|^2 E_1^{opt}} E_2^{opt} \right). \quad (15)$$

From (7) the sum-capacity of the multi-antenna MAC with sum power constraint E_T , $K=2$ users and $\mathbf{R}_H = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^H$ is

$$\begin{aligned} C_{MAC} &= \log_2 \det \left(\mathbf{I} + \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{h}_1^H \\ \mathbf{h}_2^H \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{h}_1 & \mathbf{h}_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} E_1^{opt} & 0 \\ 0 & E_2^{opt} \end{pmatrix} \right) \\ &= \log_2 \left(1 + E_1^{opt} |\mathbf{h}_1|^2 + E_2^{opt} |\mathbf{h}_2|^2 + \delta E_1^{opt} E_2^{opt} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

and $r_{2,MMSE}$ in (15) is precisely

$$r_{2,MMSE} = C_{MAC} - r_1. \quad (17)$$

With this, we end the proof that the MMSE beamformer followed by a SIC allows to reach the sum-capacity. Note that this result can be systematically generalized to any K . That is

$$\begin{aligned} r_{k,MMSE} &= C_{MAC}(1, k-1) - r_{1to(k-1)MMSE} \\ r_{1to(k-1)MMSE} &= \sum_{q=1}^{k-1} r_{q,MMSE} \\ r_{1,MMSE} &= \log_2 \left(1 + |h_1|^2 E_1^{opt} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

being $C_{MAC}(1, k-1)$ the sum-capacity of $k-1$ users.

V. FROM THE MAC TO THE BC DESIGN

Next we propose a novel design for a multi-antenna BC precoder in order to attain the sum-capacity of its dual MAC, obtained with residual matrix \mathbf{R}_{MAC} in (9) after the MMSE beamformer and sum power constraint.

First, we must pay attention to the decoding order in the MAC. If the K -th user in (9) is the first one to be decoded, because its equivalent channel r_{KK} is the strongest and can support to be decoded without cancelling the interference, then this user must be the one to be transmitted first in the BC. Note that this first user will be affected by the interference of the other users. On the other hand, if the first user in the MAC in (9) has the weakest resulting channel r_{11} , it should be the last user to be decoded, so that the rest of the other detected users can be subtracted. For this reason, this user must be the last one to be precoded in the BC, so that the interference that the other users create can be diminished as much as possible. In other words, the encoding order in the BC is the reverse of the decoding order in the MAC. Therefore, the BC channel matrix is not only the hermitian of the MAC channel matrix, but also with the reversed order of the channels

$$\mathbf{H}_{BC}^H = \mathbf{J}\mathbf{H}_{or}^H, \quad (19)$$

where \mathbf{J} is the reversed identity matrix and \mathbf{H}_{or} is the channel matrix that presents the correct decoding order. Consequently, the residual interference matrix that we aim to attain in the BC, \mathbf{R}_{BC} , must be obtained from that of the MAC as

$$\mathbf{R}_{BC} = \mathbf{J}\mathbf{R}_{Sic,MAC}^H\mathbf{J}, \quad (20)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_{Sic,MAC}$ includes the sequential interference canceller effect that nulls all the elements that \mathbf{R}_{MAC} has in its upper triangular part (i.e., $r_{ij}, i \neq j, i < j, j = 1 \dots K$). Therefore, ϵ_{ij} in \mathbf{R}_{BC} are in the upper triangular part of the matrix, and the rest of its elements are zero.

With that, we consider in the rest of the design the SVD of \mathbf{H}_{BC}^H

$$\mathbf{H}_{BC}^H = \mathbf{V}_{BC} \mathbf{D}_{BC}^{1/2} \mathbf{U}_{BC}^H, \quad (21)$$

and to simplify the notation we drop the sub-index BC in what follows.

For the design of the BC precoder, we first consider the same strategy as in the equivalent PtP MIMO to \mathbf{H}_{BC}^H . That is, we implement the architecture of (4) in order to design \mathbf{B} , the power loading is the optimal waterfilling and \mathbf{U} the right eigenvectors. With this, one could conclude that the BC sum capacity that can be obtained is the same as that of the PtP MIMO. However, the resulting equivalent channel is not diagonal and the decentralized receivers cannot cooperate to cancel the multiuser interference. Because of the MAC-BC duality we know that the interference among users cannot be null-out but reduced in order to reproduce residual interference of the optimal dual MAC (with the corresponding capacity loss with respect to the PtP MIMO)¹. Therefore, the design of the remaining matrix \mathbf{M} should be carried out hereafter such that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H}^H \mathbf{B} \mathbf{i} &= \mathbf{V} \mathbf{D}_H^{1/2} \mathbf{D}_{BC}^{1/2} \mathbf{M} \mathbf{i} \\ &= \mathbf{H}_e \mathbf{M} \mathbf{i} = \mathbf{R}_{BC} \mathbf{i}. \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Although a straightforward solution could be

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{H}_e^{-1} \mathbf{R}_{BC} = \left(\mathbf{D}_H^{1/2} \mathbf{D}_{BC}^{1/2} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{V}^H \mathbf{R}_{BC}, \quad (23)$$

this design does not preserve the total transmit power to E_T . This problem is solved with the proposed design next, which only incorporates additional orthogonal transformations together with a THP. Let us first decompose

$$\mathbf{R}_{BC} = \mathbf{D}_r \mathbf{R}_r \rightarrow \mathbf{R}_r = \mathbf{D}_r^{-1} \mathbf{R}_{BC}, \quad (24)$$

where $\mathbf{D}_r = \text{diag}(\text{diag}(\mathbf{R}_{BC}))$ and \mathbf{R}_r is an upper triangular matrix with diagonal elements equal to 1. From (22) and (24)

$$\mathbf{H}_e \mathbf{M} \mathbf{R}_r^{-1} \mathbf{i} = \mathbf{D}_r \mathbf{i}. \quad (25)$$

We compute the QR decomposition of $\mathbf{M} \mathbf{R}_r^{-1}$ as

$$qr(\mathbf{M} \mathbf{R}_r^{-1}) = qr(\mathbf{H}_e^{-1} \mathbf{D}_r) = \mathbf{Q}_a \mathbf{R}_a \quad (26)$$

¹We could argue that the power loading to be implemented in the BC should be the optimal one that has been obtained for the MAC in (7) after reversing the order, that is $\mathbf{D}_{BC}^{1/2} = \mathbf{J} \mathbf{D}_{MAC}^{opt,1/2} \mathbf{J}$. With this the BC sum capacity, which is the same as that of the MAC in (7) could be attained. This is true and gives an alternative design

and rewrite (25) as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H}_e \mathbf{Q}_a \mathbf{R}_a \mathbf{i} &= \mathbf{D}_r \mathbf{i} \\ \mathbf{H}_e \mathbf{Q}_a \mathbf{R}_a \mathbf{R}_r \mathbf{i} &= \mathbf{R}_{BC} \mathbf{i}. \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Note that \mathbf{Q}_a is an orthonormal matrix and does not modify the transmit power. However, this is not the case of \mathbf{R}_a . For this reason we define

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{v} &= \mathbf{R}_r \mathbf{i} \\ \mathbf{z} &= \mathbf{R}_a \mathbf{v}, \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

and introduce a THP to compute \mathbf{z} . It is used to limit the dynamic range of each component in \mathbf{z} with the proper design of the dynamics or modulo operation of the THP. More specifically, if $\mathbf{R}_a = \mathbf{R}_{sa} \mathbf{D}_s$ (with \mathbf{R}_{sa} an upper triangular matrix of unit diagonal elements and $\mathbf{D}_s = \text{diag}(\text{diag}(\mathbf{R}_a))$), then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R}_{sa}^{-1} \mathbf{z} &= \mathbf{D}_s \mathbf{v} \\ \mathbf{R}_{sa}^{-1} \mathbf{z} + \mathbf{z} - \mathbf{z} &= \mathbf{D}_s \mathbf{v} \\ \mathbf{z} &= \mathbf{D}_s \mathbf{v} + (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{R}_{sa}^{-1}) \mathbf{z}. \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Since $\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{R}_{sa}$ is strict upper triangular, this recursion is adequate. Now taking the modulo operation, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{z} &= \text{mod}_\rho (\mathbf{D}_s \mathbf{v} + (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{R}_{sa}^{-1}) \mathbf{z}) \\ &= \mathbf{D}_s \mathbf{v} + (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{R}_{sa}^{-1}) \mathbf{z} + \mathbf{m}\rho, \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

with \mathbf{m} a vector with positive and negative integer entries, and ρ to be designed depending on the desired dynamics of the components in \mathbf{z} . Figure 1 shows the scheme for the resulting BC precoder.

Fig. 1. BC precoder.

For the design of each of the K receivers, we formulate now the signal after transmission, that is we substitute in (1) the designed precoder. From (22) with (27) and (28)

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{H}_e \mathbf{Q}_a \mathbf{z} + \mathbf{w}. \quad (31)$$

Also, from (30) we can obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R}_{sa}^{-1} \mathbf{z} &= \mathbf{D}_s \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{m}\rho \\ \mathbf{z} &= \mathbf{R}_{sa} (\mathbf{D}_s \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{m}\rho). \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

By substituting (32) in (31)

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{H}_e \mathbf{Q}_a \mathbf{R}_a \mathbf{D}_s^{-1} (\mathbf{D}_s \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{m}\rho) + \mathbf{w}, \quad (33)$$

where we have resort to $\mathbf{R}_a = \mathbf{R}_{sa} \mathbf{D}_s$. Because of (27) we can simplify (33) and consider (34) instead

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y} &= \mathbf{D}_r \mathbf{D}_s^{-1} (\mathbf{D}_s \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{m}\rho) + \mathbf{w} \\ \mathbf{y} &= \mathbf{D}_r \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{D}_r \mathbf{D}_s^{-1} \mathbf{m}\rho + \mathbf{w}. \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

Introducing (28), we finally obtain (35)

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{R}_{BC} \mathbf{i} + \mathbf{D}_r \mathbf{D}_s^{-1} \mathbf{m}\rho + \mathbf{w}, \quad (35)$$

and the receiver of the k -th user has the structure shown in figure 2.

Fig. 2. BC receiver for user k .

Note that the signal to noise ratio at the input of the detector of user k is SNR_k

$$SNR_k = \frac{(\mathbf{D}_r)_{kk}^2}{\sigma_k^2} = \frac{(\mathbf{D}_r)_{kk}^2}{1 + \sum_{p \neq k, k < p} (\mathbf{R}_{BC})_{k,p}^2}, \quad (36)$$

where we have assumed that the thermal noise power is normalized to one. The corresponding optimal rate for this user is

$$r_k = \log_2 (1 + SNR_k), \quad (37)$$

and the obtained sum-rate in the BC is

$$r_{BC} = \sum_{i=1}^K r_k, \quad (38)$$

which is the same as the sum-capacity of the dual MAC in (7); thus, it is the sum-capacity of the BC, too.

Fig. 3. Signal constellation for a M-QAM.

In order to achieve the rate r_k , let us consider that each stream k is modulated with a symmetric M_k -QAM modulation, as the one in figure 3, which will render b_k bits per

complex symbol, with $M = 2^{b_k}$. In order to design this bit loading per stream, we must take into account that it will have associated a corresponding symbol error rate (SER), namely, $SER_k = \alpha_k Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{A_k^2}{4\sigma_k^2}}\right)$, where $Q(\cdot)$ is the Q-function, $0 < \alpha_k < 1$ is a factor that depends on the modulation, σ_k^2 is the power of the noise plus interference in the stream k , $\sigma_k^2 = 1 + \sum_{p \neq k, k < p} (\mathbf{R}_{BC})_{k,p}^2$, and A_k is the distance in volts between consecutive symbols in phase or in quadrature. The M_k -QAM presents an average symbol energy equal to $E_s = A_k^2 \frac{M_k - 1}{6}$. In our case this E_s must be set to

$$E_s = (\mathbf{D}_r)_{kk}^2 = A_k^2 \frac{M_k - 1}{6}, \quad (39)$$

in order to attain the desired rate r_k . Therefore,

$$SER_k = \alpha_k Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{A_k^2}{4\sigma_k^2}}\right) = \alpha_k Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{(\mathbf{D}_r)_{kk}^2 \frac{M_k - 1}{6}}{4\sigma_k^2}}\right) \rightarrow$$

$$M_k = 1 + \frac{(\mathbf{D}_r)_{kk}^2 \frac{6}{4\sigma_k^2}}{\left(Q^{-1}\left(\frac{SER_k}{\alpha_k}\right)\right)^2}. \quad (40)$$

With that

$$b_k = \log_2 \left(1 + SNR_k \frac{1}{\frac{2}{3} \left(Q^{-1}\left(\frac{SER_k}{\alpha_k}\right)\right)^2} \right), \quad (41)$$

which differs from the ideal rate r_k in (37) due to the penalization factor that introduces the SER_k , which can be high if raw or uncoded SER is considered. Also, additional losses may arise if, for simplicity, a square M_k -QAM is decided (i.e., half of the bits will modulate the phase and the quadrature components).

In the transmitter, each of the components of the information symbol vector \mathbf{i} (i.e., one per user stream in figure 1) is the M_k -QAM modulation that is designed following (??). Next subsection gives the details of the modulo operation.

A. The modulo operation

The role of the modulo operation is that each component of \mathbf{z} at the output of the feedback loop preserves the power of the M_k -QAM signal at input of the loop. In order to achieve this, if a value at the input of the modulo operation presents an absolute value greater than $\sqrt{M_k} \frac{A_k}{2}$ either in its phase or its quadrature component, the modulo operation will subtract $\sqrt{M_k} A_k$ an integer number of times N_k . In this case $\rho = \sqrt{M_k} A_k$.

$$\mathbf{z}_{k,mod} = \mathbf{z}_k \pm N_k \sqrt{M_k} A_k, \quad (42)$$

so that the output of the modulo operation is always in the interval $(-\sqrt{M_k} \frac{A_k}{2}, \sqrt{M_k} \frac{A_k}{2}]$. The figure 4 depicts this function.

Theoretically, at the output of a THP, the complex data symbols present an uniform distribution in the complex region

Fig. 4. Modulo $\sqrt{M_k} A_k$ function.

$(-\sqrt{M_k} \frac{A_k}{2}, \sqrt{M_k} \frac{A_k}{2}] \times (-j\sqrt{M_k} \frac{A_k}{2}, j\sqrt{M_k} \frac{A_k}{2}]$ with a symbol energy of $\frac{2M_k A_k^2}{3}$ (see [9]). In consequence, we would expect an energy penalty of

$$E_{loss,k} = \frac{\frac{2M_k A_k^2}{3}}{\frac{(M_k - 1)A_k^2}{6}} = \frac{4M_k}{M_k - 1} \quad (43)$$

per transmitted symbol and a final SER_k with the propose system of $SER_k = \alpha_k Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{A_k^2}{E_{loss,k} 4\sigma_k^2}}\right)$. However, in practice the average energy of the symbols at the output of the THP is lower because they just approximate the uniform distribution as we show in the next simulation section.

VI. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

The following numerical example illustrates the construction of the proposed precoder. Consider a scenario with 3 users (single antenna) and a transmitter with a uniform linear array of 9 antennas. In order to visualize the spatial channels, we simulate a line of sight scenario, the angles of arrival (AoA) of the users ($user_1, user_2, user_3$) are $(4, 0, -15)$, and their associated path loss $(-7.95, -3.09, 0)dB$, respectively. The total available power is 18 dBm (or $10 \log_{10}(63.0957mW)$) and the noise power is equal to 0 dBm.

A. The dual MAC

First, the channel matrix of the MAC, \mathbf{H}_{or} , is built, whose columns are the steering vectors of the users, each scaled by the corresponding path loss. The order of the columns is set based on the decreasing path loss. It is a 9×3 matrix. The MAC sum-capacity is computed based on (7) and it results equal to 17.3366 [b/s/Hz]. Next, the MMSE beamforming matrix at reception in the MAC, \mathbf{A} , is designed. Figure 5 plots each of its 3 columns or beamformers, one for each user. The resulting $\mathbf{R}_{MAC} = \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{H}_{or}$ matrix is

$$\begin{pmatrix} 5.31 & 3.76 - 7.31j & -1.37 - 2.85j \\ 0.13 + 0.25j & 5.59 & -0.71 + 0.94j \\ -0.02 + 0.05j & -0.00 - 0.01j & 13.73 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (44)$$

As we indicated in (9), the lower triangular part is the residual interference due to the MMSE beamformer, which can be visualized in figure 5, whereas the upper triangular part contains the interference that must be cancelled by the SIC.

Fig. 5. MAC MMSE beamformers for each of the 3 users. The AoA of the 3 users is shown with straight dark lines. The weakest user has an AoA equal to 4° and its beamformer does not attenuate the other two users. The second weakest user has an AoA equal to 0° and attenuates the strongest user that comes with AoA equal to -15° . The beamformer of the third and strongest user nulls out the other two.

After the SIC, the rates that are obtained for each user are

$$\begin{aligned} r_1 &= \log_2(1 + 5.3167^2) = 4.8712 \\ r_2 &= \log_2\left(1 + \frac{5.598^2}{1 + |0.1324 + 0.2573j|^2}\right) = 4.9029 \\ r_3 &= \log_2\left(1 + \frac{13.7337^2}{1 + 0.0029 + 1.0000^{-4}}\right) = 7.5625. \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

The resulting sum-rate is

$$\sum_{i=1}^3 r_i = 4.8712 + 4.9029 + 7.5625 = 17.3366 [\text{b/s/Hz}], \quad (46)$$

which coincides with the MAC sum-capacity that we have computed based on (7).

B. From the dual MAC to the BC

First, from the ordered MAC channel matrix, \mathbf{H}_{or} , we build the BC channel matrix, \mathbf{H}_{BC}^H , using (19). Also the matrix the \mathbf{R}_{BC} is obtained from (20)

$$\mathbf{R}_{BC} = \begin{pmatrix} 13.73 & -0.00 - 0.01j & -0.02 + 0.05j \\ 0 & 5.59 & -0.13 + 0.25j \\ 0 & 0 & 5.31 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (47)$$

This matrix contains the residual interference that we must obtain in the BC in order to attain the same sum-capacity as that of the dual MAC with sum power constraint. With that we begin to compute the different matrices involved in the precoder design of figure 1 and obtain the following results.

First, we compute the traditional waterfilling of a PtP MIMO with matrix \mathbf{H}_{BC}^H and obtain

$$\mathbf{D}_{BC}^{1/2} = \begin{pmatrix} 22.0911 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 22.005 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 18.9997 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (48)$$

Next, the right eigenvectors are computed. From $\mathbf{R}_{BC} = \mathbf{D}_r \mathbf{R}_r$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D}_r &= \begin{pmatrix} 13.7330 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 5.5980 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 5.3167 \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{R}_r &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -0.0007 - 0.0009j & -0.0020 + 0.0042j \\ 0 & 1 & 0.0236 + 0.0460j \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

Following (26)

$$\mathbf{Q}_a = \begin{pmatrix} -0.9073 & -0.0159 - 0.0210j & -0.1821 + 0.3780j \\ -0.3663 & -0.2652 - 0.3511j & 0.3558 - 0.7387j \\ 0.2062 & -0.5410 - 0.7163j & -0.1690 + 0.3510j \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{D}_s = \begin{pmatrix} 0.9923 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -0.8814 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1.0466 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{R}_{sa}^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0.0721 + 0.0954j & 0.1027 - 0.2133j \\ 0 & 0 & 0.7896 + 1.5352j \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (50)$$

With this, and applying (36) the next user rates are obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} r_1 &= 7.5625 \\ r_2 &= 4.9029 \\ r_3 &= 4.8712 \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

Therefore the BC sum-capacity is the same as the MAC sum-capacity, equal to 17.3366 [b/s/Hz]. Both of them are slightly smaller than the capacity of the equivalent PtP MIMO, which results in 17.339 [b/s/Hz].

If we set a $\text{SER}=10^{-5}$, and we design symmetric QAM modulations for each user stream, we obtain the following bit loading for each of the users

$$\begin{aligned} \text{user}_1 &:(2, 2) \rightarrow 16 - \text{QAM} \\ \text{user}_2 &:(1, 1) \rightarrow \text{QPSK} \\ \text{user}_3 &:(1, 1) \rightarrow \text{QPSK}. \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

These bit loadings have been obtained by resorting to (40) or (41), where we have considered $\alpha_k = 1$. Note that this is the most pessimistic design for α_k . This fact, together with constraining the QAM to be symmetric and just aiming an uncoded SER, explain that the implemented system present a sum-rate equal to 8 [b/s/Hz] instead of the optimal 17.3366 [b/s/Hz].

To finalize the explanation of this numerical example, next we comment about the THP. First, three sequences of 10^6 symbols are generated for each user, with distance $A_k=1$. Each of these sequences are normalized so that they present energy equal to 1. This sequences are multiplied by the feed-forward part of the precoder in figure 1, namely $D_s D_r$. Then the modulo operation and the feed-backward subtraction are carried out. The consequences of the modulo operation are shown in the next three figures 6, 7, 8 for the constellation of $user_1$. The obtained SERs of the described BC system are equal to 0, 3.10^{-6} , and 10^{-5} , for each of the 3 users, respectively. All of them are below the target SER= 10^{-5} .

Fig. 6. Constellation of the 16-QAM of $user_1$ after the THP.

Fig. 7. Constellation of the 16-QAM of $user_1$ at the input of the modulo operation at the receiver. The dotted square indicates the modulo operation to be carried out.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The principle aim of this paper is to introduce and illustrate a new strategy that allows a practical implementation of the multi-antenna BC precoder. Although the capacity of a channel exclusively depends on the channel and the transmitter design, the BC channel cannot attain the capacity of the PtP MIMO because the receivers do not cooperate in the BC. However, we embed the PtP MIMO precoder desing in the proposed

Fig. 8. Constellation of the 16-QAM of $user_1$ at the output of the modulo operation at the receiver.

BC in order to obtain an equivalent channel and then use the orthonormal transformations and the THP to achieve the same user rates as in those obtained with the dual MAC, when the sum-power constraint is considered (i.e., this is also called the Sato upperbound, which is attained with equality by the BC sum-capacity). Therefore, we apply MAC-BC duality but in a different way from the existing literature, in order to simplify the mapping from the MAC to the BC. The numerical results show that for the proposed example, the multi-antenna BC can achieve a sum-capacity very close to the PtP one, as intuition says. By following the same design other BC precoders can be implemented, namely the zero forcer or the qr ones. In these cases, the corresponding beamforming matrix must be designed in the MAC, and then apply duality as explained in this paper.

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